

Global Health in Crisis: On the (im)possibility of decolonizing global health

Global health has been referred to (positively) as an empty signifier capable of bringing together a variety of actors, and just as many projects, with the (general) goal of improving population health. Although this may initially seem a desirable formulation, holding global health as an empty signifier also suggests that there are no strict approaches to evaluating the impact of global health projects; judging the theoretical, political, and personal interests, presuppositions or expectations that guide global health work beyond the desire to improve, to some degree, the health of a given population; or establishing widely agreed upon patterns of continuity and discontinuity between global health and its predecessors, like colonial tropical medicine.

Using the notion of empty signifier as a starting point, this course will explore how the “emptiness” of global health either points to an existing crisis within global health, suggesting the possibility of reaching a new point of concerted action and organization towards something different, or whether global health is always already in crisis, suggesting that incomplete agreements within global health only seem incomplete because of accepted, yet unacknowledged, assumptions (e.g., what should constitute health or justice in health or the subject/object of health interventions). Under the latter, crisis also presents itself as a challenge for practitioners to either continue working under the paradigms offered by global health or finding different ways of thinking about the wellbeing of groups in an interconnected world. In other words, this course addresses a current push towards the decolonization of global health (a moment of *crisis*) and interrogates whether decolonizing global health is possible. Through select readings, we will address the constitution of global health as a historical phenomenon, explore some of the philosophical traditions that inform different approaches to population health, and address the way anthropologists have engaged with global health as practice, discipline, moral and ethical engagement, and a site of contested power relations.

Week 1 and 2: On health, “emptiness”, and crisis

Breilh, Jaime. 1994. «Las Ciencias de la Salud Pública en la construcción de una prevención profunda: Determinantes y proyecciones». En *Lo biológico y lo social: su articulación en la formación del personal de salud*, 63-100. Serie Desarrollo de Recursos Humanos 101.

Washington, D.C.: Organización Panamericana de la Salud.

Brennan, Eugene. 2024. «Crisis as Method: Politics, Temporality, and Agency». *The South Atlantic Quarterly* 123 (2): 231-54.

Edu, Ugo Felicia. 2025. «Anthropological knowledge under redaction: Meditations on race, health, and aesthetics». *Medical Anthropology Quarterly* 38 (4): 462-76.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/maq.12793>.

Fassin, Didier. 2012. «That Obscure Object of Global Health.» En *Medical Anthropology at the Intersections: Histories, Activisms, and Futures.*, edited by M. Inhorn and E. Wentzell, 95-115. Durham and London: Duke University Press.

Gordon, Jane Anna. 2014. *Creolizing Political Theory: Reading Rousseau through Fanon.* New York: Fordham University Press. (Introduction)

Gordon, Lewis. 1995. *Fanon and the Crisis of European Man: An Essay on Philosophy and the Human Sciences.* Great Britain: Routledge. (Intro, Chapter 1)

Kittay, Eva Feder. 2016. «The Liberal Autonomous Subject and the Question of Health Inequalities». En *Understanding Health Inequalities and Justice: New Conversations across the Disciplines*, edited by Mara Buchbinder, Michele Rivkin-Fish and Rebecca L. Walker, 112-34. North Carolina: University of North Carolina Press.

Masco, Joseph. 2017. «The Crisis in Crisis». *Current Anthropology* 58 (Supplement 15): S65-76.

Petryna, Adriana. 2013. «The Right of Recovery». *Current Anthropology* 54 (S7): S67-76.

Roitman, Janet. 2014. *Anti-Crisis.* Carolina: Duke University Press. (Introduction, Chapter 1)

Salm, Melissa, Mahima Ali, Mairead Minihane, y Patricia Conrad. 2021. «Defining global health: findings from a systematic review and thematic analysis of the literature». *BMJ Global Health* 6 (6): e005292. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2021-005292>.

Singer, Merrill, y Hans Baer. 1995. *Critical Medical Anthropology.* 2nd Edition. United Kingdom: Routledge. (Chapter 4)

Week 3: A history of global health (global perspective)

Packard, Randall. 2016. *A History of Global Health: Interventions into the Lives of Other Peoples.* Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press. (whole book)

Rosen, George. 1993. *A History of Public Health*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press. (Chapter 7, 8)

Week 4: A history of Global health (Latin American perspective)

Cueto, Marcos, y Steven Palmer. 2014. *Medicine and Public Health in Latin America: A History*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. (Intro, Chapter 3-5)

Armus, Diego. 2003. *Disease in the History of Modern Latin America: From Malaria to AIDS*. North Carolina: Duke University Press. (Select chapters)

Worboys, Michael. 1996. "Germs, Malaria and the Invention of Mansonian Tropical Medicine: From 'Diseases in the Tropics' to 'Tropical Diseases'." En *Warm Climates and Western Medicine: The Emergence of Tropical Medicine, 1500-1900*, edited by D. Arnold, 181-208. Amsterdam: Rodopi.

Week 5: Empire and transnational health (a transnational perspective)

White, Alexandre. 2023. *Epidemic Orientalism: Race, Capital, and the Governance of Infectious Disease*. Stanford University Press. California.

Week 6: Empire and (transnational) public health (a local perspective)

Bashford, Alison. 2004. *Imperial Hygiene: A Critical History of Colonialism, Nationalism and Public Health*. United Kingdom: Palgrave Macmillan.

Week 7: The limits of empire and transnational (public) health

Coghe, Samuël. 2022. *Population politics in the tropics: demography, health, and transimperialism in Colonial Angola*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. (selected chapters)

Pearson, Jessica Lynne. 2018. *The Colonial Politics of Global Health: France and the United Nations in Postwar Africa*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press. (selected chapters)

Week 8: Decolonizing Global Health

Grosfoguel, Ramón. 2011. «Decolonizing post-colonial studies and paradigms of political-economy: Transmodernity, decolonial thinking, and global coloniality». *TRANSMODERNITY* 1(1).

Quijano, Anibal. 1992. «Colonialidad y modernidad/racionalidad». *Perú Indígena* 13 (29): 11-20.

Richardson, Eugene. 2019. «On the coloniality of global public health». *Medicine Anthropology Theory* 6:101-18.

Richardson, Euguene. 2020. *Epidemic Illusions: On the Coloniality of Global Public Health*. Massachusetts: MIT Press. (selected chapters)

Yates-Doerr, Emily, Lauren Carruth, Gideon Lasco, y Rosario Garcia-Meza. 2023. «Global Health Interventions: The Military, the Magic Bullet, the Deterministic Model--and Intervention Otherwise». *Annual Review of Anthropology* 52:187-204.

Week 9: Decolonizing global health?

Gordon, Lewis. 2021. *Freedom, Justice, and Decolonization*. New York: Routledge. (Chapter 1, 2)

Campt, Tina, dir. 2014. *Black Feminist Futures and the Practice of Fugitivity*. Helen Pond McIntyre '48 Lecture. Barnard Center for Research on Women.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2ozhqw840PU>.

Benton, Adia. 2014. «What's the Matter Boss, We Sick?» *The New Inquiry*. 11 de diciembre de 2014. <https://thenewinquiry.com/whats-the-matter-boss-we-sick/>.

Benton, Adia. 2017. «Ebola at a Distance: A Pathographic Account of Anthropology's Relevance». *Anthropological Quarterly* 90 (2): 495-524.

Sangaramoorthy, Thurka, y Adia Benton. s. f. «Intersectionality and syndemics: A commentary». *Social Science and Medicine* 295:113783.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.113783>.

Hindmarch, Suzanne, y Sean Hillier. 2023. «Reimagining global health: From decolonisation to indigenization». *Global Public Health* 18 (1): 1-12.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17441692.2022.2092183>.

Ryneveld, Manya van, Helen Schneider, Leanne Brady, y Eleanor Whyte. 2024. «Every loaf of bread is political--Reflections on collective care responses to COVID-19 in Cape Town». *Social Science and Medicine* 349:1-8.

Week 10: Global health as political economy

Adams, Vincanne. 2016. «Metrics of the Global Sovereign: Numbers and Stories in Global Health». En *Metrics: What Counts in Global Health*, edited by Vincanne Adams, 19-48. North Carolina: Duke University Press.

Adams, Vincanne, Dominique Behague, Carlo Caduff, Ilana Lowy, y Francisco Ortega. 2019. «Re-imagining global health through social medicine». *Global Public Health* 14:1383-1400.

Oni-Orisan, Adeola. 2016. «The Obligation to Count: The Politics of Monitoring Maternal Mortality in Nigeria». En *Metrics: What Counts in Global Health*, edited by V. Adams, 82-104. Durham, N.C.: Duke University Press.

Birn, Anne-Emanuelle. 2009. «The stages of international (global) health: Histories of success or successes of history?» *Global Public Health* 4 (1): 50-68.

Buss, Paulo, y Sebastián Tobar. 2016. «Health Diplomacy in the Political Process of Integration in Latin America and the Caribbean». En *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Global Public Health*, 1-27. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Week 11: Global health as the minimum

Ruger, Jennifer Prah. 2016. «Global Health Inequalities and Justice». En *Understanding Health Inequalities and Justice: New Conversations across the Disciplines*, edited by Mara Buchbinder, Michele Rivkin-Fish and Rebecca L. Walker, 64-87. Carolina: University of North Carolina Press.

Caduff, Carlo. 2015. *The Pandemic Perhaps: Dramatic Events in a Public Culture of Danger*. California: University of California Press.

or

Redfield, Peter. 2013. *Life in Crisis: The Ethical Journey of Doctors without Borders*. California: University of California Press.

Week 12 and 13: Rethinking ethics of transnational health to move past global health

Gordon, Lewis. 1995. *Fanon and the Crisis of European Man: An Essay on Philosophy and the Human Sciences*. Great Britain: Routledge. (Chapter 4)

Gordon, Lewis. 2021. *Freedom, Justice, and Decolonization*. New York: Routledge. (Chapter 3)

Anderson, Elizabeth. 1999. «What is the Point of Equality?» *Ethics* 109:287-337.

Macleod, Alistair. 2015. «Amartya Sen on human rights in The Idea of Justice». *Philosophy and Social Criticism* 41 (1): 11-19.

Marmot, Michael. 2013. *The Health Gap: The Challenge of an Unequal World*. New York: Bloomsbury. (select chapters)

Harney, Stefano, y Fred Moten. 2013. *The Undercommons: Fugitive Planning and Black Study*. Brooklyn: Minor Compositions. (Chapter 1, 2)

Kelleher, Paul. 2016. «Health Inequalities and Relational Egalitarianism». En *Understanding Health Inequalities and Justice: New Conversations across the Disciplines*, edited by Mara Buchbinder, Michele Rivkin-Fish and Rebecca L. Walker, 88-111. North Carolina: The University of North Carolina Press.

Krause, Monika. 2023. «Theorizing from neglected cases». *Distinktion: Journal of Social Theory* 25 (2): 250-66.

Rawls, John. 1999. *A Theory of Justice: Revised Edition*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press. (select chapters)

Reid-Henry, Simon. 2016. «Just Global Health?» *Development and Change* 47 (4): 712-33.

Sen, Amartya. 2015. «The idea of justice: A response». *Philosophy and Social Criticism* 41 (1): 77-88.

Stoian, Valentin. 2014. «Property Owning Democracy, Socialism and Justice: Rawlsian and Marxist Perspectives on the Content of Social Justice». PhD Dissertation, Budapest, Hungary: Central European University.

<https://dsps.ceu.edu/sites/pds.ceu.hu/files/attachment/basicpage/478/valentinstoian.pdf>.

Wynter, Sylvia. 1984. «The Ceremony Must be Found: After Humanism». *boundary 2* 12 (3): 19-70.

Yamin, Alicia Ely. 2016. *Power, Suffering, and the Struggle for Dignity: Human Rights Frameworks for Health and Why they Matter*. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press.
(select chapters)